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Investigation of the uncommon basic properties of $[\text{Ln}(\text{W}_5\text{O}_{18})_2]^{9-}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{La}, \text{Ce}, \text{Nd}, \text{Gd}, \text{Tb}$) by changing central lanthanoids in the syntheses of pyrazolopyranopyrimidines

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Abstract

Five Lindqvist-type lanthanopolyoxometalates ($[\text{Ln}(\text{W}_5\text{O}_{18})_2]^{9-}$, $\text{Ln} = \text{La}, \text{Ce}, \text{Nd}, \text{Gd}, \text{Tb}$) complexes were prepared and fully characterized. Their basic catalytic activity was manipulated in the successful and high yielding synthesis of a series of pyrazolopyranopyrimidines via a four-component reaction, involving ethyl acetoacetate, hydrazine hydrate, benzaldehydes, and barbituric acid under ultrasonic irradiation. The catalytic activity of these catalysts with different Ln were compared under the same optimized reaction conditions in term of yields of obtained products, in shorter reaction time, indicating the superiority of the of the catalytic activity of $[\text{Tb}(\text{W}_5\text{O}_{18})_2]^{9-}$ in the aforementioned Multicomponent reaction (MCR).

Keywords: Lanthanopolyoxometalates, Lindqvist, Ultrasonic irradiations, Pyrazolopyranopyrimidines, Multicomponent reaction, Catalysis